

The COVID-19 & Cancer Consortium

Approved Project Variables

Once the project design and SAP have been approved for your project, this document will be used to specify the exact outcomes and variables to be used in your analysis. Please provide as much information as you can, including the existing variable name if you know it. Use of existing variables will decrease the amount of time that it takes to get your project to the analysis phase, but we will endeavor to add any needed derived variables based on your project needs. Existing variables can be found in two places within [the GitHub repo](#): the **Data Dictionary** (“CCC19_DataDictionary.csv”), which includes the native variables found in the survey, and the list of **Derived Variables** (“CCC19_Derived_Variables_Spreadsheet.xlsx”).

Please fill out and return this form to Jeremy Warner (jeremy.warner@vumc.org), Sanjay Mishra (sanjay.mishra.1@vumc.org) and your assigned biostatistics lead. If you need extra rows just hit Tab when your cursor is in the bottom right cell.

Primary Outcome (Table 3)

Outcome description	Outcome variable name	Outcome values
Custom ordinal outcome with death at any time	<i>der_ordinal_v1a</i>	0 = not hospitalized; 1 = hospitalized; 2 = ICU; 3 = mechanical ventilation; 4 = death at any time
Follow-up in days, with some estimation for intervals	<i>der_days_fu</i>	Integer (days)

Secondary Outcome (Table 2)

Outcome description	Outcome variable name	Outcome values	Additional Details
Derived dead/alive variable	<i>der_deadbinary</i>	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Derived variable indicating whether patient has died within 30 days of COVID-19 diagnosis (default = No)	<i>der_dead30</i>	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Derived variable indicating whether patients required mechanical ventilation	<i>der_mv</i>	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Derived variable indicating time in ICU	<i>der_ICU</i>	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Derived hospitalized/not hospitalized variable	<i>der_hosp</i>	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	

<p>Derived cardiovascular complication variable (see additional details)</p>	<p>der_CV_event_v2 (der_any_CV is the variable name in R script)</p>	<p>0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99=Unknown.</p>	<p>Derived with the following derived variables:</p> <p>der_hotn_comp, der_MI_comp, der_card_isch_comp, der_AFib_comp, der_VF_comp, der_arry_oth_comp, der_CMY_comp, der_CHF_comp, der_PE_comp, der_DVT_comp, der_stroke_comp, der_thrombosis_NOS_comp</p> <p>Coded as 1 if any of these variables is 1; coded as 0 if all these variables are 0; coded as 99 if any of variables is 99 and der_CV_event_v2 is missing; otherwise, NA</p> <p>For all listed variable here: 0=No, 1=Yes, 99=Unknown</p>
<p>Derived pulmonary complication variable (see additional details)</p>	<p>der_pulm_event (der_any_Pulm is the variable name in R script)</p>	<p>0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99=Unknown.</p>	<p>Derived with the following derived variables:</p> <p>der_resp_failure_comp, der_pneumonitis_comp, der_pneumonia_comp, der_ARDS_comp, der_PE_comp, der_pleural_eff_comp, der_empyema_comp</p> <p>Coded as 1 if any of these variables is 1; coded as 0 if all these variables are 0; coded as 99 if any of variables is 99 and der_pulm_event is missing; otherwise, NA</p> <p>For all listed variable here: 0=No, 1=Yes, 99=Unknown</p>
<p>Derived gastrointestinal complication variable (see additional details)</p>	<p>der_GI_event (der_any_Gast is the variable name in R script)</p>	<p>0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99=Unknown.</p>	<p>Derived with the following derived variables:</p> <p>der_AHI_comp, der_ascites_comp, der_BO_comp, der_bowelPerf_comp, der_ileus_comp, der_peritonitis_comp</p> <p>Coded as 1 if any of these variables is 1; coded as 0 if all these variables are 0; coded as 99 if any of variables is 99 and der_GI_event is missing; otherwise, NA</p>

			For all listed variable here: 0=No, 1=Yes, 99=Unknown
Acute kidney injury (checkbox only)	der_AKI_comp	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Multisystem organ failure	der_MOF_comp	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Any co-infection within +/- 2 weeks of COVID-19 dx	der_coinfection_any	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Sepsis	der_sepsis_comp	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Bleeding	der_bleeding_comp	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
DIC (without modifier of definite/probable/possible)	der_DIC_comp	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Remdesivir as treatment for COVID-19 ever	der_rem	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Hydroxychloroquine as COVID-19 treatment ever	der_hcq	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Steroids as COVID-19 treatment ever	der_steroids_c19	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
COVID-19 treatments other than HCQ, steroids, remdesivir	der_other_tx_c19_v2	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Indicates whether patient has ever had supplemental o2	der_o2_ever	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	

Covariate description	Variable name	Covariate values	Additional Details
Race/ethnicity including Asian	der_race_v2	Hispanic; Non-Hispanic AAPI; Non-Hispanic Black; Non-Hispanic White; Other	
Age with imputation for categoricals	der_age_trunc	Years (continuous 18-89; patients noted to be greater than 89 are set to be age = 90)	
Insurance type	der_insurance	Medicaid alone; Medicare alone; Medicare/Medicaid +/- other; Other government +/- other; Private +/- other; Uninsured; Unknown	
Derived variable for smoking status collapsing the current/former smoker variables	der_smoking2	Never; Current or Former; Unknown	
Binary obesity (BMI >= 30 or checkbox checked) indicator	der_obesity	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Cardiovascular comorbidity (CAD, CHF, Afib, arrhythmia NOS, PVD, CVA, cardiac disease NOS)	der_card	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	

Derived variable indicating whether patient has pulmonary comorbidities	der_pulm	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Renal comorbidities	der_renal	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Derived variable indicating whether patient has diabetes mellitus	der_dm2	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Performance Status	der_ecogcat2	ECOG 0, 1, or 2+	
Breast biomarkers combined variable	der_breast_biomarkers	1 = ER+; 2 = ER+/HER2+; 3 = HER2+; 4 = triple negative; 99 = Unknown	
Derived variable indicating cancer status (Splits remission/NED by cancer timing)	der_cancer_status_v4	0 - Remission/NED, remote; 1 - Remission/NED, recent; 2 - Active, responding; 3 - Active, stable; 4 - Active, progressing; 99 - Unknown	
Timing of cancer treatment relative to COVID-19, collapsed	der_cancer_tx_timing_v2	0 = more than 3 months; 1 = 0-4 weeks; 2 = 1-3 months (*); 88 = never or after COVID-19 diagnosis; 99 = unknown	
No cancer treatment in the 3 months prior to COVID-19	der_cancertr_none	0=No; 1=Yes; 99=Unknown	<p>Derived with the following covariates:</p> <p>der_any_cyto, der_any_targeted, der_any_endo, der_any_immuno, der_any_local, der_any_other</p> <p>Coded as 1 if all these variables are 0; coded as 0 if any of these variables is 1; coded as 99 if any of these variables is 99; otherwise, NA</p>
Any cytotoxic cancer treatment in the 3 months prior to COVID-19	der_any_cyto	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Any targeted therapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19	der_any_targeted	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
Any targeted therapy includes an anti-HER2 therapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19	der_her2_3m	0 = No; 1 = Yes	<p>Derived with der_her2, der_any_targeted.</p> <p>Coded as 1 if der_any_targeted is 1 and der_her2 is 1</p> <p>Coded as 0 if:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> der_any_targeted is 1 and der_her2 is 0 der_any_targeted is 1 <p>Otherwise, NA</p>

			<p>der_her2: 0 = No; 1 = Yes</p>
<p>Any targeted therapy includes a CDK4/6 inhibitor therapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19</p>	der_cdk46i_3m	0 = No; 1 = Yes	<p>Derived with der_cdk46i, der_any_targeted.</p> <p>Coded as 1 if der_any_targeted is 1 and der_cdk46i is 1</p> <p>Coded as 0 if: a. der_any_targeted is 1 and der_cdk46i is 0 b. der_any_targeted is 1</p> <p>Otherwise, NA</p> <p>der_cdk46i: 0 = No; 1 = Yes</p>
<p>Any other targeted therapy (Not anti-HER2 / CDK4/6 inhibitor) in the 3 months prior to COVID-19</p>	der_other_3m	0 = No; 1 = Yes	<p>Derived with der_targeted_not_her2_cdk46i, der_any_targeted.</p> <p>Coded as 1 if der_any_targeted is 1 and der_targeted_not_her2_cdk46i is 1</p> <p>Coded as 0 if: a. der_any_targeted is 1 and der_targeted_not_her2_cdk46i is 0 b. der_any_targeted is 1</p> <p>Otherwise, NA</p> <p>der_targeted_not_her2_cdk46i: 0 = No; 1 = Yes</p>
<p>Any endocrine therapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19</p>	der_any_endo	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
<p>Any immunotherapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19</p>	der_any_immuno	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
<p>Any local therapy (surgery or RT) within 3 months</p>	der_any_local	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
<p>Any other cancer therapy in the 3 months prior to COVID-19</p>	der_any_other	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	
<p>Region of patient residence with ex-US collapsed</p>	der_region_v2	Non-US; Other; Undesignated US; US Midwest; US Northeast; US South; US West	
<p>Trimester and year of diagnosis, using the most recent side of the interval as anchor</p>	der_tri_rt_dx	T1 2020; T2 2020; T3 2020; T1 2021	
<p>What type of area does the patient primarily reside in?</p>	urban_rural ¹	1, Urban (city) 2, Suburban (town, suburbs) 3, Rural (country) 88, Other 99, Unknown	

The type of health care center providing the patient's data	der_site_type	AMC = academic medical center; CP = community practice; TCC = tertiary care center	
Initial Severity and Course of Illness	severity_of_covid_19_v2 ¹	1, Mild (no hospitalization required) 2, Moderate (hospitalization indicated) 3, Severe (ICU admission indicated) 99, Unknown	
Derived treatment intent	der_tr_intent	Unknown Treatment; Not on Treatment; Palliative; Curative; Missing Unknown Treatment and Missing were collapsed for analysis	Derived with der_anytx and treatment_intent: Coded as "Unknown Treatment" if der_anytx is NA or 99; Coded as "Not on Treatment" if der_anytx is 0 Coded as "Palliative" if der_anytx is 1 and treatment_intent is 2 Coded as "Curative" if der_anytx is 1 and treatment_intent is 1 Otherwise, Missing der_anytx: 0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown Treatment_intent: 1, Curative 2, Palliative 99, Unclear or unknown
Most recent line of cancer treatment, including systemic and non-systemic therapies	der_txline	Untreated in last 12 months; Curative NOS; First line; Non-curative NOS; Other; Second line or greater; Unknown	
Hematologic malignancy indicator	der_heme	0 = No; 1 = Yes	

Other covariate related to cohort selection for analysis	Variable name	Covariate values	Covariate description
Sex (Recode other/prefer not to say gender --> missing)	der_sex	Male, Female	
Breast cancer	der_Breast	0 = No; 1 = Yes	
Cancer type of second malignancy. If the patient has more than two malignancies, please select the second-most recently diagnosed cancer type. If unknown or unclear,	cancer_type_2 ¹	" indicates no second malignancy.	

please specify in the free text box below			
Region of patient residence with US and ex-US collapsed	der_region_v3	Non-US; Other; US	

New covariate request – 2-5-22

New covariate	Variable name	Covariate values	Covariate description
MBC vs non-MBC	der_metastatic	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	Metastatic cancer status (only applicable to solid tumors/lymphoma)
MBC site of metastasis	der_met_bone	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	Metastatic to bone
MBC site of metastasis	der_met_liver	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	Metastatic to liver
MBC site of metastasis	der_met_lung_v2	0 = No; 1 = Yes; 99 = Unknown	Metastatic to lung

Once this form has been finalized, it will be signed by:

Approved:
 Core Lead, Informatics

Date: 2/7/2022

Approved:
 Biostatistics Analyst

Date: 02/07/2022